

EQUIVALENT WORDS BETWEEN TURKISH AND UZBEK

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ABSTRACT

The Turkish language has been divided into different dialects because of some historical and political reasons as well as various language-internal reasons from past to present. While these dialects are similar to each other in some ways, they are also different from each other in some ways. Vocabulary of dialects is noteworthy in this regard. Although some dialects match up substantially with each other in terms of vocabulary, other dialects match up slightly. The most important factor in determining this is if dialects are taking place in the same group or not. In our country, especially since the mid-90s, acceleration of translation activities' has caused recognition of other dialects' vocabularies. On the other hand these translation activities have brought with various translation problems too. Translation of false friends is at the top of these problems. These false equivalence words are used to being trap for transmitters. This study is focused on false equivalence verbs in vocabularies of Uzbek and Modern Uighur Turkish which are taken place in southeastern dialect group; between these dialects and Turkey Turkish written language, false equivalence verbs have been identified and has been focused on meaning differences. During this classification, it has been understood that these differences have happened as a result of various meaning matters such as synonymy, homonymy, polysemy. In Uzbek and Modern Uighur Turkish it has been seen that meanings of verbs are similar; but in Turkey Turkish some of these verbs have had different meanings in time, some of them have already come from different roots and therefore have different meanings. Through this study, it is hoped that it will be useful in translation studies from these dialects.

Introduction

Language is the most fundamental tool for communication between people. Each language has its own unique structure, which includes significant features that distinguish it from other languages. Turkish is a particularly rich language in this respect, with multiple synonyms for many words being quite common. This can sometimes cause indecision when translating or selecting words. In this article, we will discuss equivalent words in Turkish and examine different approaches to this issue. There are various "dialects" in the Turkish world that have emerged for various reasons and have their own unique vocabularies of words. A significant portion of the words used in Turkish dialects are similar to each other at the "basic dialect" level, with even fewer being similar at the "Common Turkish" level. However, the overlap of "similar" words in terms of conceptual field and being "equivalent" is not necessarily based on similarity by nature. (Uğurlu 2012, 215)

Methods

Different methods can be used to examine equivalent words in Turkish in English. One of them is to examine the word origins. Some words have similar meanings even though their origins are different, and in this case, equivalent word selection can be made. For example, the Arabic-origin "ak" word and the Turkish-origin "saf" word both contain similar meanings for the word "white". In studies on false equivalent words, dialects such as Chuvash, Turkmen, Azerbaijani, Nogay, Uzbek, and Kazakh have been emphasized regarding their vocabularies. It has been noted that some Turkish dialects' vocabularies do not exactly overlap and false equivalents are emphasized as elements that resemble each other in form but differ in meaning and function between two languages. Examples of false equivalent words and affixes causing disruptions in inter-dialect transfer are shown (Uğurlu 2000, 59-77; Uğurlu 2004, 20-25; Sultanzâde 2010, 166; İlker 1999, 553-559; Kirişcioğlu 2006, 21-35; Karadoğan 2004, 1591-1604; Yıldız 2009, 257-297; Resulov 1995, 916-924; Yusuf 2007, 2082-2085). Points that intermediaries should pay attention to have also been emphasized in these studies (Kara 2004; Kara 2009, 1056-1082; Ercilasun 1995, 91-100; Ercilasun 1992, 179-207). In some studies these words have been evaluated as homophones or cognate words (Kara 2004; Özkan 1999, 883-889). There are also studies that evaluate false equivalent words in the context of Turkish and borrowed words and compare these words with Old Turkish; and transfer issues are evaluated through the topics of "verb tenses", "adjective-verbs", and "adverb-verbs" (Akbaba 2007, 151-176; Alkayış 2009, 60-70). Another method is to select equivalent words according to the usage area of the word. For example, the word "yolculuk" can be considered equivalent to "seyahat" or "gezi". However, while the word "yolculuk" is used more for long-term, planned trips, the word "gezi" signifies shorter-term, unplanned trips.

Findings

False cognates arise between related languages and dialects of the same language through linguistic effects such as homophony, polysemy, semantic shifts, and loanwords. New meanings have emerged as the original meanings of the same word have become separated over time. These different meanings can be shaped by the similar and close relationships a word has formed with other objects for a period of time.

In every language, many words do not perform a single task, they are very meaningful and reflect multiple meanings (Aksan 2007, 180,182). In addition to transfers in meaning changes, social factors also play an important role. Changes in society's worldview cause concepts to transform, relationships between concepts and the signs that reflect them to disappear, and new relationships to be established.

Changes in meaning have been occurring for centuries. However, changes that occur in written language are not easily reflected in dialects and accents, where the old meaning of a word can persist for centuries (Aksan 2007, 216-217). Changes in meaning have been one of the most debated language topics since ancient Greece.

Many philosophers and linguists have focused on the elements whose meanings and functions have changed over time, researching the ways and reasons for these changes (Aksan 2007, 211). The change in meaning occurs as a result of a more or less change in the relationship established between what is shown and what is being shown, and this change usually occurs between interconnected, related concepts (Aksan 2007, 212).

In changes of meaning and the development of connotations, various semantic events such as comparison, transfer, idiom transfer (metaphor), name transfer (metonymy), polysemy, synonymy, homonymy, semantic restriction, specialisation, semantic extension, generalization, metaphorization (metaphor), meliorative change and pejorative change play a role.

Conclusion

The subject of equivalent words in Turkish is a very broad field and can be handled with different approaches. Factors such as word origins, usage areas and semantic features can be decisive in choosing equivalent words. However, it may not always be possible to make the right choice, and in this case, it is important to be careful when translating or choosing words. When reading Turkish texts with equivalent words in Uzbek, we will need to know the language in detail like this in order for our translation to be good.

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